

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Gro Haarklou Mathisen

Your email address: gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 25.08.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, data curation, methodology, visualisation

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Evidence-based chemical risk assessments are a large part of my daily work. As the toxicity data are shifting from animal studies to NAMs, I am interested in the development of tools for incorporation of such data as evidence in chemical risk assessments.

Signature

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
- (2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Camilla Svendsen

Your email address: Camilla.svendsen@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 20 June 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, data curation, visualisation

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Evidence-based chemical risk assessments are a large part of my daily work. There are a paradigm shift from using animal studies to using NAMs, also in chemical risk assessment. Therefore, I am interested in the development of tools for incorporation of data from NAMs as evidence in chemical risk assessments.

Signature

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Gunn Elisabeth Vist

Your email address: gunn.vist@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (06.06.2023):

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Data curation, Methodology, Writing-Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have no financial interests related to this publication

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am convinced of the benefits of being evidence-based in research. Otherwise, no conflicting interests pertaining to this publication

Signature

Gunn E. Vist

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Trine Husøy

Your email address: trine.husoy@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 19 06 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualisation, methodology, writing - review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Non to declare

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Non to declare

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Trini Husky". The signature is written in a cursive style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Heather Ames

Your email address: heather.ames@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 09.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "Heather J. [unclear]". The signature is written in a cursive style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Audebert

Your email address: marc.audebert@inrae.fr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 15 November 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Andebet", written over a horizontal line.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Annette Bernhard

Your email address: abe@hi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 13.11.2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am actively engaged in various research projects aimed at generating and synthesizing evidence to inform public health policy and decision-making. I am part of my organisations animal welfare committee and committed to upholding the 3R principles in research, as well as to applying rigorous systematic review methods to support the quality and integrity of this work.

Signature

Annette Benford

Notes

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This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Anna Beronius

Your email address: anna.beronius@ki.se

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 22 June 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Review and comment

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Beronius is one of the initiators and developers of the SciRAP tools for data appraisal, which includes a tool for evaluating quality of in vitro toxicity data.

Signature

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Signature page

This document has been electronically signed
using eduSign.

eduSign

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Ellen Bruzell

Your email address: Ellen.Bruzell@niom.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 12 Nov 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Investigation, writing – review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests	Non-financial interests
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	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other non-financial interests

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Insert here

I have received and will continue to receive honoraria from the Norwegian Scientific Committee on Food and Environment (VKM) for participation in systematic risk assessment and systematic mapping/scoping reviews. Honoraria for my expert role in EFSA WG on sweeteners (systematic risk assessments) goes to my institution, not to me.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

I am convinced that the use of evidence-based systematic methods in scientific research related to (particularly) human health is necessary and important to develop further. In addition to my expert roles in EFSA, from 2024 to 2025 I am a member of the WHO's Guidance Development Group of the Technical Guidance on environmentally friendly and less invasive oral health care WHO, where part of my work will be to evaluate systematic rapid reviews conducted by other experts. Currently, I am coordinating a systematic mapping review at my institute about dental restorations. I am associate editor of the journal Photochemical and Photobiological Sciences.

Signature

A rectangular box containing a handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Ellen R. Bruzell".

Notes

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This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Emma Di Consiglio

Your email address: emma.diconsiglio@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):03 07 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

The issues described in the paper partially overlap and/or are extremely useful for other projects and/or risk assessment activities (EFSA WG, EU COM), in which I am actively involved, related to the use and development of NAMs.

Signature

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Miles P. Davenport

Your email address: m.davenport@unsw.edu.au

Date of completion of form (14 Nov 2024):

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing
Supervision

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I am an employee of UNSW Sydney. I also receive reimbursement for service on panels for NHMRC (Australia). I have received payment from eLife as a senior Editor (non-current).

I receive grants from NHMRC (Australia), ARC (Australia), MRFF (Australia), NIH (USA), Wellcome Trust, CEPI.

I have received contract funding from the Australian Federal Government and NSW State Government for services relates to evidence analysis and modelling in the COVID-19 pandemic.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I work in the area of evidence assessment in vaccines / immunology (funded by NHRMC, Wellcome / CEPI). I have published in this area and have a commitment to evidence assessment practices.

Signature

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
- (2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Ingrid L. Druwe

Your email address: druwe.ingrid@epa.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 07/03/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Provided critical review and commentary

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
<input type="checkbox"/> From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="checkbox"/> From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Current and previous research findings or projects
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<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am an employee of the United States Environmental Protection Agency in the Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessments (CPHEA) where I work on IRIS chemical risk assessments and their impact on human health and the environment. Implementation of novel systematic review methods such as those being explored in this manuscript may be incorporated directly or indirectly into the systematic review methodology used by CPHEA.

Signature

Ingrid L. Druwe 07/03/2023

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: René Geci

Your email address: rene.geci@esqlabs.com; rgeci@ukaachen.de

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 12.11.2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Investigation, writing - review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

As a part of my (PhD) research, I am interested in helping to better characterise and validate the accuracy and precision of data coming from *in vitro* assays since those can be used to parameterise PBK models, which I am relying on for my research. Increased trust in and useability of *in vitro* methods thereby has the potential to benefit my future research.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Ursula Gundert-Remy

Your email address:

Date of completion of form (14 11 2024):

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Participation on three rounds of reviewing and discussing the questionnaire, reviewing the draft manuscript

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am involved in activities to strengthen the application of high-quality systematic review methods in assessing the health impact of food additives as a member and Vice-chair of a Panel in EFSA.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Thomas Hartung

Your email address: THartung@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 02 Jul 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Not applicable

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Not applicable

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'A. Maly', is written over the 'Not applicable' text.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Sebastian Hoffmann

Your email address: Sebastian.hoffmann@seh-cs.com

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 06.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing; Supervision

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

My research interests are assessment of NAM methods and EBT. I fully embrace the principles of evidence-based toxicology.

I am a member of the SOT and of the EBM commission of the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment.

The publication may affect these non-financial interests.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Helena T Hogberg

Your email address: Helena.hogberg-durdock@nih.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 14 11 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing; Resources; Data Curation

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

NA

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

NA

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. D. G.' or similar, written in a cursive style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Carlijn Hooijmans

Your email address: Carlijn.hooijmans@radboudumc.nl

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):23062023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Advice on methods

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I do not have any of the listed non financial interests. I am a scientist at the Radboud university of Nijmegen in the Netherlands, and I run the meta research team. A team that focusses on developing, applying and disseminating systematic review methodology across evidence streams, performing meta-research on research rigour and robustness principles and providing education within and beyond the Radboudumc.

Signature

A handwritten signature consisting of a stylized, scribbled initial followed by the name 'Guymans' written in a cursive, handwritten style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Lucina E. Lizarraga

Your email address: Lizarraga.lucina@epa.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 12 Nov 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Investigation; writing – review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Not Applicable

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have a commitment to the use of systematic review (SR) principles and approaches that promote scientific rigor and transparency in environmental risk assessment. I routinely incorporate SR into my assessment work and actively participate in a workgroup that supports the development and implementation of SR methods and tools to support assessment science within the EPA's Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS).

Signature

 Recoverable Signature

X Lucina E Lizarraga

Signed by: LUCINA LIZARRAGA

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Jennifer Olker

Your email address: olker.jennifer@epa.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 18 Nov 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing – review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have no financial interests that could be affected by the publication.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have a commitment to identifying and using the best available data for chemical decision-making. As a researcher at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's Office of Research and Development, I lead the ECOTOX Knowledgebase team that uses systematic review approaches and transparent, reproducible methods to identify, review, curate, and evaluate ecological toxicity data for use in risk assessments and criteria/benchmark development. I am also the co-chair for the U.S. EPA's Systematic Review Community of Practice, which provides a forum for practitioners across EPA to share knowledge and experience on the frameworks, practices, and implementation of "fit-for-purpose" systematic reviews. In addition, my research at the U.S. EPA has included development and implementation of high-throughput in vitro screening assays for targets relevant for thyroid disruption. My experience with in vitro screening assays and systematic review methods for ecological hazard assessments led to and informed my participation in this project.

Signature

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Pilar Prieto

Your email address: pilar.prieto-peraita@ec.europa.eu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29 06 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Final review

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'P. In', written over a horizontal line.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Joshua Robinson

Your email address: joshua.robinson@ucsf.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29 06 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
<input type="checkbox"/> From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/> From litigation or legal cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Publicly held positions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have received funding from the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and other sources which support the development and application of in vitro toxicological assessments. Thus, I have

a financial interest in the overall growth of in vitro science field for toxicology and chemical risk assessment.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am a member of the Society of Toxicology and the Society of Birth Defects Research and Prevention. Both of these societies support the development of the in vitro science field for toxicology and chemical risk assessment.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'JFR', written over a light blue horizontal line.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Andrew A. Rooney

Your email address: andrew.rooney@nih.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 20 Jan 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Supervision; Writing – review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests as indicated by lack of "X" above.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

One non-financial interest as indicated by "X" above as I am employed in the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) in the National Institute of Health (NIH) of the United States of America. I am the Chief (acting) of the Integrative Health Assessments Branch of the Division of Translational Toxicology in the U.S. NIEHS in the NIH. The views expressed are my own and do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the U.S. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'C. J. Y.', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Adriano S Sebollela

Your email address: asebollela@gmail.com

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 16 Nov 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

methodology, writing - review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am currently involved in a project intended to systematically review in vitro studies on beta-amyloid peptide neurotoxicity. I am a member of BRISA (Brazilian Reproducibility Initiative in preclinical Systematic review and meta-Analysis), a network aimed to conduct and provide training on systematic reviews and meta-analysis to the Brazilian biomedical sciences community.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'ASSE', followed by a long horizontal line extending to the right.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Nicola Margareta Smith

Your email address: nicolamargareta.smith@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 12 Nov 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Not applicable

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am an early career researcher with a commitment to advancing evidence-based approaches in regulatory toxicology. In my current and likely future roles, I anticipate using the tool (or similar) under development in this manuscript, as they align closely with my focus on rigorous systematic review methods and high-quality evidence synthesis. These tools, can impact research findings but I doubt my involvement with this manuscript will change any current research outcomes

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink on a light-colored background. The signature reads "Nicola Smith" in a cursive, slightly slanted script.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Eliana Spilioti

Your email address: e.spilioti@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 08/06/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above
No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Anastasia Spyropoulou

Your email address: a.spyropoulou@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):08.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Olga Tcheremenskaia

Your email address: olga.tcheremenskaia@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 03/07/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Being involved in several institutional activities and projects under OECD (on AOP, IATA, in silico NAMs) that aim to increase the confidence in NAMs with the purpose of using them in risk assessment procedures, the issues described in the papers partially overlap with my other interests and are of great interest for my current work.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Olga Tcheumina". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial 'O'.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Amy Wang

Your email address: huishan.wang@nih.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 12 Nov 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

methodology, writing - review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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Non-financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I conduct systematic reviews and contribute to the refinement of systematic review practice and tools. I am an NIEHS employee in the Integrative Health Assessment Branch (IHAB), Division of Translational Toxicology. IHAB is known for its devotion to better systematic review. I am a member of Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration, US EPA-led Systematic Review Community of Practice, and GRADE Working Group. I reviewed manuscripts related to systematic review for NIEHS internal clearance/review and for scientific journals. I was a co-chair or member of IARC monograph working groups, and a member of the Science Advisory Committee on Chemicals to peer review the revised draft EPA TSCA Systematic Review Protocol.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Amy Zwing". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Johanna Zilliacus

Your email address: johanna.zilliacus@ki.se

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 17 November 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Publication on SciRAP in vitro tool: Roth N, Zilliacus J, Beronius A. Development of the SciRAP Approach for Evaluating the Reliability and Relevance of in vitro Toxicity Data. *Front Toxicol.* 3:746430, 2021. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2021.746430.

Course director of course on Weight of Evidence and Systematic Review Methodology in Health Risk Assessment of Chemicals, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden.

Signature

See electronic signature below

Notes

(1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.

(2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.

(3) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.

(4) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail, but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the contributor should state they are unable to complete the form.

Signature page

This document has been electronically signed
using eduSign.

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Declaration of Contributor Interests

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form.

Personal details

Your name: Paul Whaley

Your email address, for contact purposes: paul@whaleyresearch.uk

Date of completion of this form (DD MMM YYYY): 3 February 2023

Contribution to the Research Project

Conceptualisation, methodology, writing - original draft, writing - review and editing, visualisation, supervision

Interests

Place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the SR?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially conflict with the objectives of the SR?	
X	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.		Deeply held beliefs or convictions
	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	x	Current and previous research findings or projects
	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	x	Commitments to specific standards or processes
	From litigation or legal cases		Publicly held positions
	From grants		Personal relationships
	Other financial interests	x	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
		x	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
			Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have or am providing consultancy services for: the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public Health; Lancaster University, mainly around securing impact of the research I was doing for my PhD (completed 2020); and for Yordas Group, to deliver training in SR methods for EU JRC. I also receive an Honorarium as Editor in Chief for the journal *Evidence-Based Toxicology* (EBT), to which this manuscript is being submitted. I am setting up the Institute for Evidence-Based Toxicology, a non-profit company based in Germany. The company will begin trading in 2023, and I am one of 4 Directors with a 25% share in the business. The work of the company will be providing services relating to evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental health.

In general, my consultancy work is around development and promotion of systematic review methods in environmental health research, delivering training around these methods, and providing editorial services. While relevant to the present work, I am not aware of any way in which these interests could compromise the integrity of the research I am undertaking here.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have a general public commitment to high quality systematic review methods in support of environmental health policy and decision-making, and am actively involved in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in evidence synthesis. I have developed conduct standards (e.g. COSTER), reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage, PRIVAT) to support the production of high quality systematic reviews and evidence maps. I am an active member of the GRADE Working Group, an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy in the UK, have a senior role at EBTC that involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental health; similarly, my role at the journal EBT involves high-profile public advocacy for evidence-based approaches to evidence synthesis that includes advocating for the use of study appraisal instruments, of which the present manuscript is an example. In general, I have a strong interest in supporting precautionary, evidence-based approaches to environmental health policy. While relevant to the present work, I am not aware of any way in which these interests could compromise the integrity of the research I am undertaking here, as the standards implied by the work are consistent with those to which I have expressed public commitment.

Signature

SIGNED

Notes

(1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.

(2) Contributors to a SR should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in a SR project.

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